

“MAGISTRLAR” CERTIFICATE OF AWARD

We hereby present this certificate to

Begmuratova Erkinay Kurbanbaevna

**Maktabda kimyo faning muammoli-integrativ
o'qitish usullari**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

